

02/11/21 Myco gDNA Extraction

SAMPLE	NAME OF SAMPLE	COND.	K-DNA	FROM	RESULT
1	FL24.24 P17 FFP3	CP	YES	GP	NEGATIVE
2	Mel1 INS-GFP TBX3-/- c17 p61	CP	NO	SM	NEGATIVE
3	TMD146 Pre-Sendai	cp	yes	AG	NEGATIVE
4	2103-331-3D LCLs	cp	yes	AG	NEGATIVE
5	KOLF2.1 iPSC Holzbauer Lab	cp	no	Outside lab	NEGATIVE
6	CHOPWT15.2 (P27, FFP2)	cp	no	AG	NEGATIVE
7	H1 PP1 C25 P5	CP	YES	CO	NEGATIVE
8	MOCK				NEGATIVE
9	NEGATIVE CONTROL				NEGATIVE
10	POSITIVE CONTROL				Positive

please send for CNV

02/11/21, Mycoplasma PCR by Cathy, gDNA digestion 1h

